

POLICY BRIEF

Translating Climate Services Policies into Actions: Recommendations from Seven Living Labs in Europe and Africa

Actively engaging users in producing climate services is effective in increasing the actual use and impact. The need for advancing the provision and use of climate services to build a climate-smart and resilient future is gaining increased recognition as climate change continues to pose increasing threats to societies, economies and ecosystems. There has been considerable progress in recent decades, but the practical use of climate services to support the implementation of climate change resilience and adaptation policies and plans remains a major challenge. There is an urgent need of alignment between local, national and global policy actions. Equally important is the promotion and strengthening of collaboration across multiple actors. Enhancing progress in these arenas is necessary to allow for context sensitive co-creation of climate services that translate into evidence-based decision-making. This policy brief outlines three actionable recommendations (Box 1) to catalyse the co-creation and use of climate services to address multiple climatic and hydrological risks at local level.

Hydroclimatic risks and the frequency and intensity of extreme events such as droughts, heatwaves, wildfires and floods are growing globally. Europe is no exception. Many countries in Europe, including France, Italy, Spain, Portugal, and the United Kingdom, to name a few, were heavily impacted by one or more climate related hazards in 2023 and 2024. These were also the planet's two hottest years on record, to date. Climatic hazards coupled with other factors such as social, economic, geo-political and ecological vulnerabilities pose major risks to many sectors such as agriculture, water management, environment, tourism, health, energy and infrastructure. Addressing climate and water related risks across scales (global to local) is a major challenge. To address these, policies, plans and strategies aim to mitigate and adapt to current and future climate related risks, and strengthen human capacity and resilience against disasters. Examples include the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate

Change, the Paris Agreement, the SENDAI Framework, the Sustainable Development Goals, and the European Union's Climate Adaptation Strategy and corresponding National Adaptation Plans. Development, provision and use of climate services in decision-making is widely recommended in such policy instruments. However, translating these strategic frameworks into concrete actions requires considerable time and effort, due to the need for broad stakeholder engagement, institutional coordination and behavioural or institutional change. Implementation must account for these requirements to ensure effective and sustainable uptake of climate services. When effectively implemented, climate services can facilitate the mindset, the process, and the achievement of change by promoting action-oriented approaches that help reinforce the alliance between institutions and users. This collaborative dynamic is essential to build trust and capacity and ensure that policies translate into impactful actions on the ground.

Box 1. Three key policy recommendations stemming from the co-creation of climate services in seven countries in Europe and Africa.

1. Strengthen local hydroclimatic monitoring data and information systems, and promote their use in climate service co-creation and decision-making processes.
2. Integrate climate services informed decisions in developing and implementing adaptive and proactive policies, plans and strategies.
3. Raise awareness of climate services, knowledge, tools and applications available to aid decision-making, and enhance capacity of different sectors and decision-makers to use them.

Over the last decades, climate services (representing a range of information such as seasonal forecasts, climate projections, climate monitoring and reports, extreme event forecasts, and more) have been developed to inform climate policies and adaptation actions. For example, the European Union's Copernicus Programme provides climate services and open data that help in monitoring the climate and its evolution in real-time, and upcoming changes from seasons to decades ahead, through seasonal forecasts and climate projections, for Europe and beyond. Despite this progress in the generation of climate services, their use in policy, planning and decision-making is still limited. This can be due to various factors, such as a lack of involvement of decision-makers in their development resulting in their being unsuitable for the intended use, concerns about their reliability, and the absence of, or limited access to, sector-specific information at the spatial and temporal scales relevant to the needs of the decision-maker.

The policy recommendations presented here stem from the experiences and lessons learned during the co-creation of user-centred climate services in seven countries in Europe and Africa. This work has been undertaken in the Netherlands, Spain, Italy, Hungary, Greece, Georgia and Lesotho under the European Commission funded I-CISK (Improving Climate Services through Integration of Local and Scientific Knowledges) Project.

Strengthen local hydroclimatic monitoring data and information systems, and promote their use in climate service co-creation and decision-making processes

The integration of local and global data and information in climate services enhances their saliency, credibility and legitimacy. These three dimensions are important to increasing the likelihood of their use in decision-making and in the development of effective policies, plans and strategies. The investments and efforts on developing, providing and sustaining both global and local data and information systems should go hand in hand, as both are not just complementary but highly interdependent. Evidence from the I-CISK project suggests that sub-seasonal to seasonal climate predictions can be improved by training global tools and models or post processing model outputs using local data. Moreover, a sound understanding of decisions made by the users and underpinning local and global knowledges are instrumental in co-creation of user-centred climate services. However, in many cases, such as in some regions of Spain and Georgia, local and global data, information and knowledge systems are not sufficiently developed, not well maintained or are not easily accessible. This limits the provision of relevant information required to co-create user-centred climate services that are fit for the user needs, contexts and local scales. For example, information on groundwater systems and how these

Box 2. Policy options stemming from Andalucía-Los Pedroches study area in Spain.

- Improve open data policies to expand access to climate related information generated by the Spanish meteorological service, currently only available for public authorities or for a fee. This will allow end-users to adapt climate information to their needs.
- Increase the topographic and geographic diversity of the observation network sites to better capture complex terrain and variability in landscapes.
- Increase the spatial resolution of climate information. The current climate information from regional models is not adequate to understand the local impacts of climate change.
- Improve estimates of increases in water demand in dryland farming under climate change scenarios in river basin management plans.
- Improve the characterisation and monitoring of complex groundwater systems of limited productivity, like the Los Pedroches aquifer, by river basin authorities.
- Improve special drought management plans by including more diverse adaptation actions and disaster risk reduction protocols.
- Urgently address climate change related challenges of the Dehesa agroforestry systems in current climate change adaptation plans and strategies.
- Consider climate projections for improving risk management in protected areas, for resilient forest planning and climate adapted reforestation actions.
- Provide climate services with tools to allow comparison between the past and the future, and develop sector specific climate information.

Action on these can significantly contribute to the update and implementation of relevant policies and plans such as The Spanish National Climate Change Adaptation Plan 2021-2030, Andalusian Climate Action Plan, River Basin Management Plans and Special Drought Plans for Guadiana and Guadalquivir river basins.

Box 3. Policy options stemming from the Alazani-lori river basin in Georgia.

- The National Environmental Agency should upscale the meteorological and hydrological monitoring network by installing additional stations in strategic locations. This will enhance real-time data collection and ensure the availability of historical climate and hydrological records for future analysis, model improvement and climate services development.
- Georgian agriculture and related departments (e.g., irrigation and drainage) should better plan their irrigation scheduling activities and improve water related infrastructure operation and maintenance based on the streamflow prediction information.
- The Scientific-Research Centre of Agriculture may analyse and translate streamflow prediction information generated by the National Environmental Agency to user friendly language.
- The Rural Development Agency should provide information to farmers and other local stakeholders through the Information Consultation Centres based on the information received from the Agriculture Scientific Research Centre and other national and local agencies.
- National Environmental Agency could inform Biodiversity Department of Ministry of Environmental Protection and Agriculture of Georgia in case of drastic changes in streamflow in order to make further actions for biodiversity conservation.

Relevant policies, plans and strategies include, but not limited to, the 2030 Strategy of Climate Change of Georgia and 2024-2025 Action Plan, Agriculture and Rural Development Strategy 2021-2027, Water Resource Management Law of 2023, and Strategy and Action Plan for the Protection of Georgia's Biodiversity.

function under increasing climate variability and extreme events (e.g., droughts) is needed by users from the agriculture, livestock and natural area management sectors in Los Pedroches, Spain. This information is critical to make informed management and investment decisions on resource use under changing hydroclimatic patterns. The users in Los Pedroches would also benefit from access to other climate services, such as spatially refined climate information and drought outlooks, to guide their seasonal, annual and long-term decisions for the management of the Dehesa agro-forestry system, livestock production and olive groves farming. Similarly, the evidence from Alazani-Iori river basin in Georgia points to the urgent need of strengthening sparse hydroclimatic observation networks, alongside investment in the operation and maintenance of irrigation and drainage systems. Integration of local datasets into globally available climate services and data are a prerequisite to improve the accuracy of streamflow prediction systems and drought outlooks at sub-catchment to river basin scales in Georgia. Boxes 2 and 3 provide a few policy options for Spain and Georgia, which could be instructive for catalysing the development and use of climate services for the examined study areas and elsewhere with similar contexts.

Integrate climate services informed decisions in developing and implementing adaptive and proactive policies, plans and strategies

While several global and regional policy and governance instruments (e.g., SENDAI Framework, European Union's Climate Change Adaptation Strategy) indicate the need and value of investing in the development and use of climate services, the incorporation of climate services informed decisions is often lacking in national to local policies and plans. Moreover, disaster risk reduction and management practices are mostly reactive and focus on crisis management. The transition towards proactive and adaptive risk management policies and practices are recommended by many countries across the world, including in Europe. Examples of relevant references from the European Union include the Water Framework Directive, Floods Directive, Blueprint for Safeguarding European Waters, Strategy on Adaptation to Climate Change, and the Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change. However, actual progress in proactive disaster risk reduction and management is slow and highly variable within and across countries. One of the major bottlenecks is the lack of the explicit consideration of climate services and how these can be used to effectively inform potential measures in the national, river basin, sectoral and local plans and strategies. Addressing these issues can catalyse climate-smart decision-making, avoid

or minimise the negative impacts of multiple hazards and accelerate progress in building resilient societies, economies and ecosystems.

The I-CISK experience from Emilia-Romagna study area in Italy highlights the concerns of local stakeholders about increasing seasonal streamflow variability and hydrological droughts. This poses challenges in equitable and sustainable water allocation among competing water use sectors (e.g., agriculture, water supply, energy and environment). The Italian experience also indicates the potential for embedding climate services developed by the project in existing regulatory and planning tools, such as Resilience Plans and Regional Water Protection Plans, as a way to reduce emergency rationing and streamline authorisation procedures, thus enabling a shift from reactive to forecast-based water governance. The experience demonstrates that climate services have the potential to enhance policy frameworks for water governance, fostering climate resilience and proactive resource management. Moreover, co-creation approaches provide a concrete opportunity to strengthen alliances between institutions and end-users by fostering shared responsibility in planning and decision-making. This institution–user collaboration is key to advancing effective, equitable and resilient water governance. Co-created sub-seasonal to seasonal streamflow forecasts can provide useful information to guide reservoir water storage and release decisions and develop optimal water allocation strategies. This type of information can be considered by a range of decision-makers towards coordinated and coherent planning and climate services informed decisions within and across multiple water

Box 4. Specific policy options emerging from the I-CISK experience in Emilia-Romagna, Italy

- Integrate climate services into relevant national, sectoral and local plans by using sub-seasonal and seasonal forecasts to optimise water storage, distribution and allocation among competing sectors to build preparedness and resilience against drought and water scarcity.
- Facilitate the adoption of forecast-based water governance. This could be achieved by establishing pre-authorised measures within relevant plans to reduce bureaucratic burdens and conflicts among stakeholders during emergency situations.
- Invest in co-creating and implementing climate services and digital solutions by capitalising on multiple funding sources available within the existing budget allocations or explore new funding sources. Develop incentive mechanisms for water users adopting climate services informed (e.g., forecast-driven) management approaches.
- Encourage synergies between climate services and other existing services, such as irrigation advisory services, agricultural extension systems, and civil protection mechanisms. This further enhances the integration of climate-informed decision-making into existing operational frameworks.

These recommendations are of specific relevance for local Water Protection Plans, Resilience Plans, and Rural Development Programmes and the implementation of the European Union's Water Framework Directive and Common Agricultural Policy in Italy.

Box 5. Specific policy options emerging from the I-CISK experience in Crete, Greece

- Strengthen coordination at institutional and local levels, under every aspect of coherent policy making and collaborative planning regarding climate change adaptation and resilience building aspects for multiple sectors (e.g., tourism, water management, agriculture, infrastructure, environment and energy). Promote co-design principles for the development of programs of measures under various policies and plans.
- Incorporate climate risk assessment in land use planning and licensing of new tourism infrastructure in vulnerable areas. Make climate risk screening mandatory for new tourism investments in coastal and water sensitive areas. Integrate risk assessment in spatial planning (local spatial plans) and in the environmental assessments for licensing.
- Consider creation of a regional data hub for hydroclimatic risks, providing open access data and information for stakeholders and citizens. This can be coordinated by the Regional Climate Change Observatory or the Hellenic Centre for Marine Research. It can support monitoring, early warning and dissemination of tailored services.
- Water management and other sectors should integrate climate services in their planning and operations. For example, water supply and irrigation agencies can use sub-seasonal and seasonal forecasts to optimise water storage and allocation, develop drought scenarios with predictive thresholds for triggering measures, train technical staff in the use of climate services, and adopt forecast-based governance practices in management plans.

These recommendations are of specific relevance for policies, plans and strategies related to tourism, water management, and climate change adaptation in Crete, Greece.

use sectors and scales. Furthermore, the evidence from Crete, Greece, suggests the urgent need for tourism and related sectors to incorporate a variety of climate and hydrological services (e.g., sub-seasonal to annual and long-term information on precipitation, temperature, wind and streamflow) to guide both operational and investment decisions in a manner that contributes to sustainable and climate resilient development in the region. Boxes 4 and 5 outline specific recommendations emerging from Italy and Greece.

Raise awareness of climate services, knowledge, tools and applications available to aid decision-making, and enhance capacity of different sectors and decision-makers to use them

Awareness raising and capacity development of all actors (e.g., developers, brokers, investors and users) involved in the climate services co-creation process are central to developing innovative and user-centred climate services and provide a solid foundation on which their maximum benefits can be harnessed. The experiences during

the I-CISK project highlight that awareness raising and capacity development needs exist in all the focus areas in Europe and Africa. Climate service developers often lack sufficient understanding of user needs and of the policy, planning and decision-making contexts. At the same time, climate service users, including citizens and decision-makers, lack adequate knowledge of available climate services, and their value and usefulness to inform decision-making. Both developers and users should be made aware of the potential of co-creation processes to tailor climate services to meet the current and future user needs.

The I-CISK project clearly highlights the awareness raising and capacity development needs while providing actionable insights to address them. Awareness raising on climate variability and change, adaptation planning and the potential role of climate services in dealing with climate and water extremes was recognised as an important need by the decision-makers. Actively participating in the co-creation of tailored climate services contributes to raise awareness and bridge knowledge and capacity gaps. Co-creation activities carried out in the Netherlands facilitated enhanced awareness and coordination among multiple actors representing the water authority, and the tourism and agriculture sectors. In Lesotho and Georgia, organizing workshops and demand driven trainings addressed specific capacity development

needs of national meteorological focal points. In Hungary, communication and dissemination activities using surveys, heat mapping campaigns and outreach through social media were important tools to raise awareness about growing heatwaves risk and potential adaptation measures. Moreover, climate services brokers play an important role in understanding the needs of decision-makers and communicating those needs to the developers of climate services for consideration. At the upstream end, developers of climate services enriched their knowledge of the user needs and how to address these in the provision of tailored climate services. A careful selection of participatory activities fitting to the co-creation context is very important in bridging awareness and capacity gaps. From the I-CISK co-creation experience, the recommended set of participatory activities may include surveys, interviews, focus group discussions, workshops and meetings (online & in-person), participation in local events, national and regional conferences and open days, field visits and collaboration with local organisations, tailor-made trainings, mentorship programmes, outreach through social media, support in developing and updating (contingency and risk management) plans and operating procedures, and cross-learning from multiple actors within and across case studies.

Methodology

This policy brief has been developed as part of the I-CISK research and innovation project funded by the European Commission. The objective of I-CISK is to develop a next generation of user-centred climate services to address multiple climate and water related hazards and risks, following a social and behaviourally informed approach and co-creating these with users. The research in the project on which the insights in this policy brief have been based is grounded in seven Living Labs, established in the Rijnland, the Netherlands; Los Pedroches, Spain; Emilia-Romagna, Italy; Crete, Greece; Budapest, Hungary, Alazani-Iori Basin, Georgia; and Senqu Valley, Lesotho. In each of these, the project has been collaborating with multiple actors representing decision-makers from various sectors including agriculture, water management, forestry, tourism, energy, disaster risk reduction and others. A framework for co-creation of user-centred climate services has been developed in the project, and tested and refined with these stakeholders while co-creating a number of pre-operational climate services.

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Further information and reading

For further information, readers are directed to the website of the I-CISK project: <https://icisk.eu>, where relevant publications and communication materials can be found.

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